

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY THROUGH BUDGET TAX POLICIES

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Annotation

the article covers the essence of Budget-Tax Policy and its importance in the development of the country's economy.

Keywords

financial policy, Budget-Tax Policy, taxes, budget.

In the following years, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing consistent reforms aimed at creating an economy based on market relations. The reform strategy includes comprehensive support of State Economic Policy. One of the most important of such Dastak is the consistent financial policy of the state. In the context of liberalization of the economy, special emphasis is placed on the problems of conducting state financial policy and financial regulation of the economy.

Financial policy plays a key role in organizing tasks that must be completed in order to bring the goals set to life. In the process and implementation of financial policy into life, it manifests itself as a weapon that affects economic interests, providing conditions for the performance of tasks that are in the society. The main direction of financial policy is to increase the efficiency of the use of financial resources, redistribute among the spheres of the financial system and have a general direction.

Financial policy professors a.V.Vahobov and T.S.Malikovs defined:"the processes of formation, distribution and redistribution of social wealth to meet the individual needs of reproduction and provide the continuous reproduction process with financial resources, are called financial policies to determine the resolution of the goals and objectives to be pursued"

Professor of the nature of financial policy t.S.Malikov and P.T. The jalilovs expressed the following opinion: “the most fundamental feature of financial policy is that it should be aimed at continuously influencing the development of the country's productive forces and economic success.”

Another tariff can also be assigned to financial policy as follows: methods of using finance, practical forms of its organization and a set (sum) of methodological principles are called financial policy.

In some cases, financial policy is interpreted as a certain activity of state bodies, which is related to the performance of the functions of the state-to the use of financial resources. Such an interpretation carries several risks in itself.

As a component (direction) of financial policy, the budgetary policy of the state is determined, first of all, in accordance with the Constitution of each country, and other laws that determine the functions of the bodies of isolation in the budgetary process and in legislative creativity. Despite being a big business in terms of its size and importance, it is not advisable to consider budget policies as exclusive to the budget process. The law provides for the functions of legislative and executive bodies in power in the budget process, the functions of subects of the country, the principles of budgetary federalism, the rights and obligations of subects of the budget process, etc.K.must clearly define the S. However, budgeting is not limited to this. Budget policy is accumulated in the budget, which is expressed in determining the contribution of the budget, in the relations of the upper and lower bodies of the country,in the structural structure of the budget expenditure part, in the distribution of expenses between budgets of different levels, in the management of the state, in determining ways to cover the budget deficit.

Budgetary policy-ensuring the implementation of the principles of organizing budgetary relations, is the sum of methods, measures and targeted activities of the implementation of the goals and objectives facing the state and society through the state budget. Budgetary policies can vary at different stages of the development of the state and society, varying depending on the level of socio-economic progress.

Budget policy:

- * budget revenue policy;
- * budget spending policy;
- * public credit policy;
- * budget deficit management policy;

The policy of organizing inter-budgetary relations is carried out on the basis of the harmony of the like.

So, budgetary policy is a component of State Financial Policy and is the sum of measures and main directions of the state aimed at the formation and involvement, distribution of public financial resources (resources), their intended use. The main goal of the budget policy is the wealth created in society.

Tax policy is the most important part of financial policy. Tax policy is the sum of measures, activities related to the organization of the development and adoption of decrees, laws and decisions of the state on the taxation system in accordance with the state economic policy, ensuring their implementation.

The state tax policy should actively affect the stabilization and development of the Republic's economy, the comprehensive support of entrepreneurs, the improvement of the standard of living of the population.

Consequently, tax policy is not only the automatic implementation of tax laws, but also their improvement.

In the experience of World tax policy, the main emphasis is on the following areas of taxation: солиқларнинг фискалик даражасини камайтириб бориш;

- creating favorable opportunities and economic conditions for financial economic activities of economic sub-entities; adaptation to the market for the production of competitive products;
- creation of financial resources necessary for the implementation of the tasks of the state in the socio-economic sphere;
- create conditions to eliminate the problem of employment, help the underprivileged;
- to ensure the improvement of the standard of living of the population, to increase non-taxable minimums depending on the level and opportunities of economic development;

Increasing the number of substances entering the “istemol basket”, etc.

The strategic task of the state tax-budgetary policy is to purposefully influence the market economy and its infrastructure, which is developing in order to ensure the structural restructuring of state funds, economic independence and, ultimately, an increase in the well-being of the population. Here, budget-tax policy is understood as the focus of the state in the field of improving taxation in order to optimally formulate budget revenues and rationalize government spending.

At the moment, the tax-budgetary policy should be aimed at increasing the efficiency of the Wai on the cultivation of Labor, increasing the income of legal entities and individuals in order to expand the taxable base. The feature of the budget-tax policy is that it is necessary not only to ensure the state's income base

and cost the money earned, but also to ensure macroeconomic stability in society and a low level of inflation, optimal employment of the population.

Tax-budgetary policy in a narrow sense, macroeconomic stability is aimed at ensuring universal Macroeconomics, such as economic growth, ensuring structural changes in the economy, foreign economic activity and a gradual foreign exchange market, ensuring stable material well-being of the population and increasing social protection of the population.

In terms of implementation of tax-budgeting in practice, it is important to determine the correct compliance between primary tasks in other words, Budget-Tax Policy

In the context of a market economy, the main tasks of tax-budgetary policy are to avoid the decline of the production process in the economy, to develop measures aimed at stimulating production. To do this, measures such as lowering tax rates in the field of tax policy, granting tax benefits for new investments, applying accelerated depreciation are carried out.

- As characteristic features of the tax-budget policy in Uzbekistan, the following can be distinguished:

- government socio-economic and Budget-Tax Policy interlinked and complementary;

- the focus of tax-budgetary policy on achieving and strengthening the promotion of macroeconomic stability and economic growth;

- organization of tax collection in a rational way and ensuring the stimulating role of taxes;

- the orientation of budget expenditures on social purposes.

The incentive tax-budget policy will be aimed at eliminating the periodic fall of the economy or increasing the costs of the state budget due to the reduction of taxes. The limiting tax-budget policy, on the other hand, will be aimed at lowering the inflation rate due to tax increases or limiting the periodic rise in public spending and economic growth.

In conclusion, tax-budgetary policy forms the basis of the country's financial system. The rational use of existing financial resources, improving the efficiency of their correct orientation and achieving the integrity of tax-budgetary relations in ensuring positive and economic development serves to ensure macroeconomic stability in the country, maintain an effective tax and Budget Policy, raise the standard of living of the population.

REFERENCES:

1. Т.Маликов, Н.Хайдаров. Давлат бюджети. Т.: "IQTISOD-MOLIYA, 2007
2. Н.Х.Хайдаров. Роль иностранных инвестиций в финансовом оздоровлении Узбекистана. Финансы и кредит, 2001
3. Nizamiddin Khaydarov. Agricultural Development in Uzbekistan: Agricultural Reforms versus Transboundary Water Issues. Developing Country Studies www. iiste. org. ISSN. 2015
4. Ҳайдаров Н.Х. Молия: умумдавлат молияси. Т.: Иқтисод-молия, 2009
5. Т.Маликов, Н.Хайдаров. Давлат бюджети. Т.: "IQTISOD-MOLIYA, 2007
6. Ortiqov Ulug'bek Akrombek o'g, Muzaffarov Muhammadjon Maxmud o'g'li, Kamolov Maqsudjon Murodullo o'g'li. Davlat xaridlarini tashkil etishda korrupsiyaga qarshi kurash. Journal of Universal Science Research, 2023/9/22
7. Samadov Ortiq, Muzaffarov Mukhammadjon. Analysis of the Participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Processes of International Economic Integration. Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 2023/5/13
8. Muhammadjon Muzaffarov. Davlat xaridlarini tashkil etish shakllarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. Science and Education, 2022/12/31
9. O'roqov Uchqun Yunusovich, Moyliyev Murod Baxtiyorovich, Muzaffarov Muhammadjon Maxmud o'g'li. Mamlakat investitsiya jozibadorligini oshirish orqalixalqaro kapitalni jalb qilish masalalari. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal / ISSN 2181-0842 June 2022 / Volume 3 Issue 6
10. Urokov Uchkun Yunusovich, Toshmatova Rano Gaipovna, Sharapova Mashhura Azadovna, Ismailova Nasiba Komiljonovna, Isaev Husan Mansurovich. MATTERS OF REVENUE GENERATION AND COST OPTIMIZATION WHILE INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE STATE BUDGET. Journal of Hunan University (Natural Sciences) Vol 2021
11. УЮ Уроков, КР Чинкулов. Узбекистонда давлат харидларининг такомиллашувининг ҳуқуқий асослари. Халқаро молия ва ҳисоб» журнали, 2017
12. Ortiqov Ulug'bek Akrombek o'g, O'sarov Javohir Bahodir o'g. AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARINING KORPORATIV MOLIYAVIY STRATEGIYASINI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.

Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 2023

13. У.А. Ортиқов Ойбек Ҳамлетов. ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ЭКО-INNOVACIY OSNOVY I OPYT VEDUSHCHIH STRAN. «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ» 2023/06/03

14. Ortiqov Ulug'bek Akrombek o'g'li, Xasanov Jaxongir Jamshidovich. KORXONA RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH TIZIMI (ERP) ORQALI BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISH. World of Science, 2023

15. Улуғбек Ортиқов, Жаҳонмирзо Мирзахалимов. КОРХОНАЛАРДА ХОДИМЛАРНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ ИҚТИСОДИЙ УСУЛЛАРИ. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2023

16. УА Ортиқов, СИ Кўчқоров. ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ЭКО-ИННОВАЦИЙ ОСНОВЫ И ОПЫТ ВЕДУЩИХ СТРАН. оности образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2023

17. Улуғбек Ортиқов, Суннат Эсанбеков. КОРПОРАТИВ БОШҚАРУВ ТИЗИМИНИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ҚЎЛЛАШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ. Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education, 2023

18. Ulug'bek Ortiqov, Yulduz Nasimova. RISKNI BARATARAF ETISHDA B2B BIZNES MODELINI QO 'LLASH MEKANIZMLARI. Наука и инновация, 2023

19. Ulug'bek Ortiqov, Ismoil Ismoilov. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI JORIY ETISH SHAROITIDA KORXONALAR MOLIYAVIY HOLATINI TAHLIL ETISH. Наука и инновация, 2023

20. Sharifov Umid Ashur o'g'li Ortiqov Ulug'bek Akrombek o'g'liBYUDJET IJROSINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI. «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ». Выпуск №10

21. Namozov Feruzbek Ashurovich Ortiqov Ulug'bek Akrombek o'g'li. O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI MOLIYA BOZORLARIDA UCHRAYOTGAN MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH. «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ» УДК 37 ББК 94

22. Ортиқов У.А. Жиянова Н.Э. СОЛИҚ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЖАХОН ТАЖРИБАСИ ВА УНИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН АМАЛИЁТИДА ҚЎЛЛАШ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ. ИННОВАЦИИ В ЭКОНОМИКЕ, 2020

23. УА Артиқов, НЕ Джиянова. ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ СВОБОДНЫХ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОН В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН. ББК У. Ят31+ ЧЗ4Я431 А 43

24. Azamat Ostonokulov. Improvement of methodology for accounting of extra-budgetary resources of public educational and medical institutions. E3S Web Conf. Volume 296, 2021 Management and Green Technologies (ESMGT 2021)
25. BK Hamdamov, AA Ostonokulov, Byudjet nazorati. O'quv qo'llanma. T.: "Iqtisod-Moliya", -318 b
26. O'roqov Uchqun Yunusovich, Moyliyev Murod. "Baxtiyorovich, Muzaffarov Muhammadjon Maxmud o'g'li." Mamlakat investitsiya jozibadorligini oshirish orqali.
27. Muhammadjon Muzaffarov. Davlat xaridlarini tashkil etish shakllarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. Science and Education, 2022/12/31
28. Muzaffarov Muhammadjon Maxmud o'g'li, Ortiqov Ulug'bek Akrombek o'g, Mavlonov Doston Mavlon o'g'li. INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB QILISHDA QULAY INVESTITSIYA MUHITINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI, World of Science 2023/10/4